

Role of Field-Trip Strategy in Promoting Effective Teaching and Learning of Business Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

This study is qualitative research which relies on available literature. It focuses on role of field-trip strategy in promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions. It dwells on business education, field-trip strategy as well as teaching and learning of business education at tertiary level of education. It also establishes that field-trip strategy can promote effective teaching and learning of business education because it motivates the learners to try new things and retain what they have already learnt, gives room for practical experience, enables lecturers to use resources in the community to make teaching to be more meaningful, enhances curriculum enrichment, encourages provision of current office materials for teaching purpose, avails lecturers with relevant information which will aid illustrations in the classroom and provides opportunity for hands-on learning. The study concludes that field-trip technique could serve as a recipe for promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions due to the fact that it makes the lecturers to play the roles of moderators, while the students play active roles leading to acquisition of the desired skills. Finally, the study among others recommends that lecturers should adopt field-trip as part of their teaching strategies, field trips should be properly and adequately planned and lecturers who wish to use the strategy should be supported by their schools' managements and parents/guardians.

Keyword: Role, Field-trip, Effective teaching, Learning, Business education.

Introduction

Acquisition of functional skills for positive performance leading to rapid transformation of human society is the fundamental goal of education all over the world. This can be achieved through teaching and learning. This is because Gidado et.al (2016) state that both teaching and learning are the most important activities in the educational enterprise and they contribute to the generation, transmission and application of knowledge. For teaching to be effective in order to enhance the attainment of educational goals (learning), numerous strategies can be adopted by the teachers in line with the peculiarity of the message to be passed to the learners. Business education is a skill-based programme which is sometimes regarded as an education for and about business. It is also practical based which requires the students to see some things for themselves as they occur in the field so as to make them to exhibit better performance after graduation either as self-employed or employees of organizations. To achieve this goal, field trip/excursion is among the effective strategies for teaching and learning of business education. This owes to the fact that the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) in Gidado et.al (2016) stresses that field-trip makes it possible for a teacher to use resources in the community to make teaching to be more meaningful and allow the students to have concrete experience and practical illustrations of theoretical skills they have acquired in the classroom.

Role of Field-Trip Strategy in Promoting ... (Gidado, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687425>

Field-trip is a student-centered approach to teaching which puts the learner in position of dominance with the teacher playing the role of a moderator. In addition to this, a deduction from Kehinde and Salami (2020) shows that the learner-centered method allows the learners to play active roles in the teaching-learning process, while the teacher carries out passive roles in the sense that it gives the learners the opportunities for discussing, debating and questioning. Omo-Ojugo and Ohiwerei in Gidado et.al (2016) are of the opinion that the use of expository method in teaching business education which puts the teacher in control is ineffective and it negatively effects students' perception of the practical aspect of business education. This is because it does little in advancing conceptual understanding and critical thinking.

In addition to the aforementioned, constructivism theory is a student-centric strategy which can lead to effective teaching and learning. According to Ekpenyong and Edokpolor (2016), the basic tenet of constructivism is that students construct their own knowledge in relation to the information or idea of the subject matter that is presented to them rather being mere passive receivers of information from a given source. Based on this, the authors state that information cannot just be deposited in the heads of the learners. It has to be discovered through activities that are meaningful to them. In line with this, they assert that people develop their knowledge through active participation in learning. Furthermore, Ekpenyong and Edokpolor point out that there is no single constructivism theory, but they all agree that students are active in constructing their own knowledge and social interactions are important in knowledge construction process. Application of this theory is therefore useful in the educational system. This because when its principles are applied by a lecturer using field-trip as a teaching strategy to teach business education in tertiary institutions, teaching and learning would be effective. This owes to the fact that it allows the lecturer to take advantage of the learners' previous knowledge while preparing for the excursion. It also enables the learners to break new grounds by themselves through relating their entry behaviours (classroom experience) with what is practically done in the industry thereby making them to relate theory with practice so as to have clear pictures of the concepts that were theoretically discussed in the classroom. It is thus, based on the aforementioned that this paper focuses on the role of field-trip strategy in enhancing effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Business education is one of the major components of vocational education and it is viewed differently by people and institutions based on their views and exposure. This shows that there are numerous definitions of business education. According to Ibrahim in Obi (2020), business education is a programme of study which aims at equipping its products with multiple skills for teaching or working in industry as well as being able to establish businesses as entrepreneurs. Chiaka and Tiku (2020) also posit that business education is an aspect of general education which has the goal of equipping the learners with distinctive skills, knowledge, aptitude and attitudes that are required for occupational competence in areas of education and business. In the same vein, Azuka and Obi in Azuka (2020) are of the view that business education is an academic programme that is made up of four components namely; creation of occupational awareness, preparation of youths for work in business, preparing people to become better citizens and consumers of goods and services as well as production of business teachers. A look at these definitions reveals that at the tertiary level of education, business education is a course of study which has the goal of enhancing human capital development which would all things being equal bring about sustainable development in the society. This is because the products have the chance of acquiring skills necessary for societal progress in the educational enterprise through serving as educational administrators and teachers. The products can also work in the government's Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) and the private sector or become self-reliant through setting up their businesses.

Field-trip Strategy at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

The major objective of field-trip is to enable an individual to be exposed to different environments, learn and be able to try new things. Field-trip is embarked upon by scholars, researchers and students for the purpose of accessing firsthand information on a given research or curriculum content in an industry, factory, museum, archeological, geographical or historical sites. In line with these, Aliyu in Gidado et.al (2016), states that field-trip is a process of visiting or taking trip(s) to a place(s) where relevant teaching material could be found in the sense that not all materials could be found within the four walls of the classroom. In addition to this, a deduction from Dasun et.al (2023) reveals that field-trip is an instructional strategy that allows students to discover things by themselves thereby getting firsthand knowledge on a given subject component through visiting places outside the normal classroom. Upula (2023) also states that field-trip deals with taking students outside the classroom in order to enable them to make relevant observations and obtain specific information. Similarly, deduction from Momozoku et.al (2022) shows that it is an educational adventure which is organized by the school and gives the learners the opportunity of going out of the school premises in order to interact with what they learnt theoretically in the classroom through physical

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manipulation and or participation, work in a team or co-operatively with others and get experience that might not be possible in the classroom. Finally, the steps involved in field-trip include; trip selection, logistics planning, field-trip preparation/pre-trip discussion, field-trip, post field-trip and evaluation of field-trip. From the foregoing, it is obvious that field-trip is a strategy that enables the students of tertiary institutions to move out of the confines of their classrooms and school environments in order to see things for themselves and enhance the attainment of the objectives of a given curriculum.

Teaching of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education

Teaching is a challenging but rewarding profession in which a teacher plays an important role of helping learners to acquire and develop knowledge and skills that would be useful and applicable in future. According to Akinpelu in Abdulkadir (2017), teaching is a deliberate attempt by an experienced person (teacher) to impart knowledge, information and skill unto a less experienced person (learner), in line with this, Salami (2016) sees teaching as an activity carried out by an agent (teacher) whose primary aim is to at the end of an experience modifies the behaviour, feeling and or thinking of an audience (learner). Furthermore, a deduction from Enyekit and Enyekit (2019) shows that teaching attempts at bringing about desirable changes in the behaviours of the learners which improves and transforms the learners as well as the society so as to enhance qualitative changes which would result into sustainable development in the society. Similarly, Vin-Mbah in Buba and Hamman (2019) holds the view that teaching is a multi-purpose occupation which focuses on human resource development and economic growth. It could be deduced from the aforementioned that at the tertiary level of education, teaching of business education is carried out by teachers (lecturers) who guide the students into learning. Teaching of business education is therefore said to be effective, if positive change in behaviour, attitude and conception is noticed in student(s) through the ability of analyzing, developing, creating and demonstrating understanding for personal and societal progress.

Learning of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Learning is a continuous process which begins at birth and ends at death. It is shaped by experience in the sense that experience is used in dealing with new situation or condition and developing new relationship(s). It is based on this that Bingham and Corner in Malamed (2016) point out that learning is based on input, process and reflection and it is what changes us. This owes to the fact that it is a transformative process of taking information which when internalized and mixed with what we have experienced, would change what we know and build on what we do. Similarly, Clark and Mayer in Malamed (2016) are of the view that learning has to with strengthening correct responses and weakening incorrect ones. It also involves adding new information to a person's memory and making sense of the presented material by attending to relevant information, mentally reorganizing it and connecting it with what they have already known. From the foregoing, it could be seen that learning can occur in both the formal and informal set up. This is because; a person could gain and internalize an experience(s) anywhere. It should however be noted that at the tertiary level of education, it results from an interaction(s) between the teacher (lecturer) and the learner. It is based on this that Salami (2016) sees learning as a change in behaviour which arises due to the interaction between the teacher and the students in the classroom. This implies that the interaction would lead to acquisition of knowledge and skills and also enable the learners to readily make them available from memory for the purpose of solving future problems and utilizing opportunities. To corroborate this, Buba and Hamman (2019) are of the assertion that learning is all about change which is brought about by coming up with skills, change in an individual's attitude and societal development. It is worthy of note that these are among the goals of education at the tertiary level of education

Field-Trip and Effective Teaching and Learning of Business Education at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria

Field-trip is a teaching method whose purpose is to promote effectiveness in teaching and learning. As deduced from Momozoku et.al (2022), field-trip enables the learners to have the desire for trying new things and retain what they learnt. A deduction from Cooke-Nieves in Kasumu and Kasumu (2023) also states that field-trip gives room for practical experience of actual performance of work processes through observation which stimulates the desire to learn and leads to actual learning. In line with these, when the interests of business education students in tertiary institutions are aroused; curiosity would be ignited leading to acquisition of effective skills that are needed for efficiency in the discipline which are expected to make them to be highly productive and competitive after graduation. The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) in Gidado et.al (2016) also states that field-trip enables a teacher to use resources in community to make teaching to be more meaningful and allows students to have practical experience and illustrations of how things are done in organizations so as to compliment the theoretical skills they acquired in the classroom. Furthermore, Aliyu in Gidado et.al (2016) is of the view that field trip is used due to the fact that not all learning resources are available within the four walls of the classroom. In the context of business

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education at the tertiary level, the possible places where students could be taken to on excursion include; factories, industries, accounting firms, offices, business organizations, post office, financial institutions and other business-related outfits. This is a manifestation of the fact that field-trip could promote effective teaching and learning of all aspects of business education such as accounting, commerce, entrepreneurship, insurance, marketing, office practice/procedure, secretarial duties/administration and word processing. Based on this, if a lecturer chooses to use the strategy, it would allow the students to observe, classify, collect data, study relationship and manipulate objects. It will also allow the students to learn on the basis of seeing for themselves. In line with this, seeing is said to be “believing” which implies that practical experience which creates lasting impression in the minds of the learners will all things being equal make learning of business education at the tertiary level of education to be effective.

In addition to the aforementioned, field-trip can promote effective teaching and learning of business education at the tertiary level through enhancing curriculum enrichment, encouraging the provision of current office materials for teaching purpose, availing the lecturers with relevant information which will aid illustrations in the classroom and providing opportunity for hands-on learning. These imply that the strategy can give rise to information that can lead to curriculum improvement which could make tertiary level business education to be tailored towards the need of the industry and the entire society, it could make the school administrators, government or private proprietors do away with obsolete instructional materials and provide the current ones for teaching. Furthermore, the lecturers will be exposed to new ideas that will enable them to give relevant and practical examples in the classroom. Lastly, it helps in enabling the learners to acquire psychomotor skills. This will therefore make them to have practical touch of what they learnt theoretically in the classroom.

Conclusion

Business education is a skill-based course which could be taught and learnt using different strategies. Field-trip allows the teachers to use community resources which are not available in the school to teach and make it possible for the learners to get practical touch of the theoretical knowledge they learnt in the classroom. The strategy could lead to effective teaching and learning of the business education at the tertiary level of education and the implication of these is that field-trip is a recipe for promoting effective teaching and learning of business education in Nigerian tertiary institutions in the sense that it makes the lecturers to serve as moderators, while the students play active roles leading to better acquisition of the desired skills.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing as well as the conclusion which was drawn, the following recommendations are suggested as the way forward:

1. Lecturers should ensure that they adopt field-trip as part of their teaching strategies so as to enhance effectiveness in teaching and learning activities.
2. Lecturers should ensure that field-trip is properly planned and executed.
3. Lecturers who are willing to use field-trip should always be supported by their schools' managements.
4. Parents/guardians should support the lecturers by allowing their children/wards to participate in field-trip.
5. Students should be properly briefed on the nitty-gritty of the field-trip.

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